

The Turing Way Leadership summary 2022

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The Turing Way (<https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome>) is an open source, open collaboration and community-driven handbook on reproducibility in data science and research, led by Dr Kirstie Whitaker and Dr Malvika Sharan. The project's governance is represented by a [core team](#) of 20+ members (that includes the staff and volunteer leaders), more than 400 project contributors and thousands of project users from around the world. They involve and support a diverse community of contributors and collaborators from different organisations across academia, industry and government dedicated to sharing and facilitating research best practices, tools and infrastructure.

Reproducibility is necessary to ensure the highest quality of research outcomes. Different stakeholders in research, including funders and publishers, are beginning to require that publications include access to the underlying methods, data and the analysis workflow. The goal is to ensure that all results can be easily accessed, openly examined and built upon by others in future work. Researchers should also integrate considerations of the societal and ethical implications of their work, facilitate collaboration, and maintain a transparent reporting process. This is easier said than done; conducting fully reproducible research requires a common understanding of open technology, project management, collaborative development, ethics and data skills that are often not widely or practically taught. *The Turing Way* project fills this gap by promoting quality in research by sharing practices that make data-driven research accessible, comprehensible and beneficial for everyone. In 2018, The Alan Turing Institute – the UK's National Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI) – was awarded funding to undertake and apply data science and AI research that can transform four key areas of science, industry and government. *The Turing Way* guide was founded by Dr. Whitaker originally as a guide for reproducibility, one of the core requirements for translating research into cross-disciplinary innovation. Since its launch in 2019 as a collaboratively written online guide to reproducible data science, *The Turing Way* has blossomed into a comprehensive handbook with a series of guides on project design, communication, collaboration and ethical research, as well as a community handbook. Shared under the open licences (MIT and CC-BY 4.0), everyone can freely read, reuse, distribute, modify, and contribute back to the resources. All contributions to the book are facilitated via the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way>).

Dr. Whitaker now is the director of Tools, Practices and Systems (TPS) Research Programme which represents a cross-cutting set of initiatives which seek to build open source infrastructure that is accessible to all and to empower a global, decentralised network of people who connect data with domain experts. Dr. Sharan, who originally started as the community manager of *The Turing Way* in 2019, now leads a team of Community Managers in TPS who contribute toward building interconnected systems of open-source software, datasets, communities and processes. Under their leadership, *The Turing Way* is a flagship project at The Alan Turing Institute. Their team members join The Turing Way core teams and help ensure that best practices are embedded across all projects at the Institute and the broader data science ecosystem. Supported by The Turing Way community manager, **Anne Lee Steele** and the programme manager, **Arielle Bennett**, all TPS members drive the adoption of open, reproducible, ethical and inclusive approaches in research projects by collaborating with different groups working across training, academic engagement, public policy, research engineering, EDI (Equality Diversity & Inclusion) and health research in the UK. They also mentor and support researchers to contribute back to *The Turing Way* in a bi-directional model of peer knowledge exchange. Long-term investments are being made by the institute to establish a **Practitioners Hub** ([read the proposal for details](#)). This effort will extend the impact of *The Turing Way* by creating opportunities for data practitioners and their organisations to enhance awareness of best practices and promote quality in research through cross-sector collaboration.

The Turing Way project is a working example of team science, using a wide community to define the standards and expectations the community would like to see in responsible, ethical and quality research practice. The Turing Way guides seek to provide all the information that researchers need at the start of their projects to ensure that they are conducting research that is easy to reuse and reproduce at the end. *The Turing Way* team hasn't produced these guides by choosing a select group of people to decide what is "best practice". Their success lies in the diversity of

contributors, the contributions they make to the project and the impact seen on the wider STEM sector. Managed by a core team of 18 members from The Alan Turing Institute and more widely from the international volunteer community, *The Turing Way* now boasts over 325 contributors, who have collectively written over 260 pages across 54 chapters to date. All collaborations and development processes occur in open, challenging the disconnected and isolated nature of the traditional academic research process. Contributors include researchers, open science practitioners, educators, policymakers and data experts across academia, government and industry, in various domains, at all levels of seniority, representing countries including Australia, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, India, the Netherlands, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Uganda, UK, USA, Venezuela and beyond. Based on web traffic monitoring coupled with references in more than 100 online publications, 30+ citations in peer-reviewed articles and personal testimonials, *The Turing Way* has thousands of users worldwide in academia, industry, open communities and the public sector.

The Turing Way is increasingly being recognised for influencing practices at national and international research organisations including government, funders, policy and healthcare sectors. *The Turing Way* was referenced in the Mayor of London's [Emerging Technology Charter](#), Reproducibility of scientific results in the EU, Innovation Scholars funding call by UKRI, The Health Foundation, The Carpentries, Open Life Science and the Netherlands eScience Center. The handbook and community model have been inspiring several similar resources, including the [Quality Assurance of Code for Analysis and Research](#) by the Office for National Statistics, [FAIR Cookbook](#) for the life sciences, a [guide to running citizen science projects](#) for research libraries, [The Environmental Data Science Book](#) and other international initiatives. More recently, *The Turing Way* was recommended in the Goldacre Review commissioned by the Secretary of State for Health and Care in the UK for using health data for research and analysis. *The Turing Way* was highlighted in the context of addressing a range of specific challenges around open working, the limits of open code, and the strong positive relationship between open working methods and innovative commercial activity within the healthcare sector. An impact report from the institute highlights *The Turing Way* in advancing collaborative approaches for the [people-centred approaches driving forward data ethics](#).

The *Turing Way* team employs a decentralised governance process that avoids individual authorship in favour of establishing shared ownership and agency in the project. They ensure that all contributions are fairly acknowledged, especially when their roles involve hidden labour in research that is often undertaken by members from marginalised communities in research and tech spaces. The *Turing Way* book is attributed to *The Turing Way* community with each contributor listed as the author. Most of them have been personally mentored by the core team members and all community members are given training and leadership opportunities within the project. All of their works are conducted in an inclusive and participatory manner that sets apart *The Turing Way* as a positive force for changing research culture. Their community engagement approach has empowered diverse individuals from different backgrounds, identities and lived experiences to express their viewpoints, fairly represent different realities in research and particularly involve voices from communities that have been in the past systematically excluded from STEM. All of this is helping to put *The Turing Way* in front of as many students, researchers, project leaders and educators as possible. The global reach is reflected in nearly 3000 monthly users of the book worldwide and 20,000 cumulative downloads of *The Turing Way* resources from Zenodo. *The Turing Way* received an OpenUK Award for Belonging and was highly commended by the HiddenRef Award for recognising the importance of hidden labour in academia.

The Turing Way team hosts a smorgasbord of virtual events for contributors to share ideas: weekly co-working calls for working groups led by members of the core team, fortnightly collaboration cafés, and twice-yearly, multi-day 'Book Dash' events. These are participatory platforms for respectful co-creation and celebration of community-led work and ensure that international participants have an equal chance to participate flexibly from different time zones. The Book Dash participants are offered accessibility grants, including access to high-speed internet, childcare grants, live transcription services, and subsistence costs. The event design and support have enabled participants from African, Asian, European, Latin and North American countries to contribute. *The Turing Way* incorporates universal design principles in all their resources, considering online accessibility, language and disability requirements. In 2021 alone, members of the core team delivered 11 training workshops and 39 conference talks, and the handbook is being translated by volunteer leaders into Spanish, Arabic, Portuguese and Chinese, with several more localisation interests in the pipeline. New for 2021-2022 was monthly 'Fireside Chats': informal webinars organised on topics including research infrastructure, multilingual data science and community collaboration. These conversations allow *The Turing Way* in extending its impact and aligning the wider research community with its values. By convening experts as well as engaging with open science initiatives such as The Carpentries, Open Life Science, NASA - TOPS, Code for Science

and Society, Society of RSE, Jupyter, 2i2c, Metadocencia and other communities internationally, The Turing Way project team is impacting a collective action towards improving knowledge in research reproducibility that promotes quality in research.

Relevant Links:

- Online Book (website): <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome>
- Project repository: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way>
- Impact stories:
 - [Changing the culture of data science](#)
 - [Better Together: The people-centred approaches driving forward data ethics](#)
- Overview of The Turing Way resources and communication channels: <http://bit.ly/turingway>
- Other resources:
 - Quarterly reports: https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way/tree/tps-report-2020/project_management/quarterly_reports
 - Zenodo under CC-BY license: <https://zenodo.org/communities/the-turing-way>
 - YouTube channels with project resources and updates: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPDxZv5BMzAw0mPobCbMNuA>